

SYSTEM OF VOWELS IN DIALECTS OF THE KHANS' PERIOD

Based on the works "Shajarayi Turk" and "Shajarayi Tarokima" by Abulghozi Bahadirkhan

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Abstract. This article talks about the vowel system in the works "Shajarayi Turk" and "Shajarayi Tarokima" by Abulghozi Bahadirkhan. In addition, valuable points about the vowel system in the old Uzbek language sources are presented and analyzed.

Keywords: vowels, vowel phonemes, longness, shortness, tongue back, lower wide, non-labialized vowel, long-shortness, narrow-width.

Introduction: One of the main reasons why there is no definite conclusion about the vowel system in all Old Uzbek language sources is that the Old Uzbek script, based on the Arabic alphabet, used only three letters to represent all vowel sounds. In addition, certain normative rules for expressing vowels have not been developed. That is why it is still difficult to make a scientific conclusion about vowels in the old Uzbek language. In this regard, the opinions and arguments of our Turkologists contradict each other.

For example, professor A.K. Borovkov shows that there are 8 vowel phonemes in the language of Alisher Navoi's works¹. It is noted that in the works of Professor H. Doniyorov, there are 11 vowels in the old Uzbek language, including the works of Alisher Navoi, and 9 of them have phonemes. E. Umarov, while noting that the number of vowel phonemes in the language of Alisher Navoi's works is 9, based on the vowels reflected in "Mukokamat ul-lughatayn" and based on the theoretical information presented in this work, indicates that it is 13². Academician Alibek Rustamov writes in his works devoted to the problems of the Alisher Navoi language that there were 9 vowel phonemes in the old Uzbek language³.

In the process of researching the vowel system in the language of Abulghozi Bahadirkhan's works "Shajarai Turk" and "Shajarai Tarokima", it is appropriate to compare them with the vocalism of the language of Navoi's works, as well as Alisher Navoi's theoretical information about vowels in the Turkish language (in the old Uzbek language). Because the importance of Alisher Navoi's information about this is that he thoroughly knew the system of sounds in the Turkish language, both in a practical and a theoretical nature, as a great intellectual of the people who know this language as their mother tongue. In addition, comparing the vowel system in the language of Abulghozi Bahadirkhan's works "Shajarai Turk" and "Shajarai Tarokima" with the language of other writers who created the old Uzbek language clearly shows what peculiarities arose in the phonetic system of the Uzbek literary language during the Khans period.

In the works of Alisher Navoi, in particular, in "Muhokamat ul-lughatayn", unique information about vowels in the old Uzbek language has been preserved. As a result of collecting

¹ Боровков А.К. Наваи – как осноположник узбекского литературного языка. Т.: 1976. с. 64.

² Умаров Э. "Мукокаматул -луғатайн" да ақс этган унлилар \ \ Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. 1994 .№ 4.26-28-бетлар.

³ Рустамов А. XV аср тили вокализми. \ \ Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти масалалари. 1968. № 6; Наваий тилининг фонетик хусусиятлари. Т.: Фан, 1963.

and organizing them, valuable information about the vocal system of the 15th century can be obtained. For example, the poet writes the following about the qualities of the vowel "a": "In one of the sentences, there is a relationship between alif and ho, so that a word can be rhymed with alif at the end, but the word aro ارا can be rhymed with sara سره and dara (qir-gorge) دره"⁴. From the above example, the poet informs that there are two vowels "a" in the old Uzbek language. And finally, found in the poet's works, for example, in the preface of Alisher Navoi's autograph of the poet, which is kept in the Sultanate Library in Tehran, "alifi mamduda" (ا) is written with a long "a": if we take into account the words: āg'uluq اغولوق, ātsa اتسا, ālmishtur الميشتور it turns out that there were three types of vowel "a" in the 15th century.

Long ā, short ä, simple a. Mahdikhan, as well as Persian farhangs compiled in Central Asia, confirm the existence of long ā in the 15th century. Mahdikhan shows long ā in the middle of the word through kashida that is the term stretched. In Persian farhangs, the long a in Turkish words is represented by two alif. Of these, the words represented by the alif sign are considered independent phonemes, as they have the ability to distinguish meaning. The other two are variants of the short ä phoneme that appears through at the beginning of the word - the maddali alif and at the end of the word - "hoyi havvaz".

Through the following excerpts from the works of Abulghozi Bahadirkhan's "Shajarayi Turk" and "Shajarayi Tarokima", we can get information about the vowel a and its phoneme variants in the literary language of the Khans era and compare them with other monuments of the old Uzbek language, in particular, the vocalism of the language of Alisher Navoi's works: "After his father, he became the king of the whole nation. Mountain Ar and Mountain Kar, in this age, the Great Mountain and the Little Mountain stood and spread. When it was winter, they spent the winters on the shores of Black sand and Sir water. During the time of Karakhan, the people became unbelievers, and there was not a single Muslim among them." (SH.T. p. 17).

Looking at the places where the vowel a is used in the above passage, we see that there is a phonetic system typical of all stages of the old Uzbek language in the works of Abulghozi Bahadirkhan. In particular, we find all three of the vowels a noted by Alisher Navoi:

1. At the beginning of the word "ā" is represented by the maddali alif letter. According to the classification of vowels in the old Uzbek language, this vowel sound is a back tongue, lower wide, non-labial vowel sound. This sound is more common in original Turkish words than in borrowed words. In the text above, both vowels in the word given in the form of "father" are actually back tongue, lower wide, non-labial vowels, i.e. ā. This word is still pronounced this way in Khorezm dialects today. Also, in the following words in the passage, this vowel is used with a back tongue, lower wide, non-labialized vowel: Ota, Ar tog'i Kar tog'i, ani, Ulug' tog', Kichik tog', tururlar, ani, yoylar, bo'lg'anda, Qora qum, yoqasi, qishlar, Qoraxon, andog', qolmay (Father, Mountain Ar, Mountain Kar, ani, the Great Mountain, the Little Mountain, stood, ani, spread, when it is, Black sand, shores, winters, Karakhan, became, there was not).

When the poet writes about the labial vowel, he points out that there were four independent labial phonemes in the Uzbek language of the 15th century and cites the following examples: " تور to'rki, domdur, yana تور to'rki, andin daqiqroqdurki, qush o'ltutur yig'ochdur va تور to'rki andin daqiqroqdur – uyning to'ridur va تور to'rki, barchadin ariqdur: to'rlug'ni yo eshikni turmak uydur (تور it is four, domdur, else, تور it is four, it is better than it, the bird is a dumping wood and تور it is four, it is better than it - the front of the house and تور it is four, thin than everyone: the house is

⁴ Алишер Навоий. Асарлар .14-том.Т.: 1966. 114-бет.

the home center or the door)»⁵. As it can be seen from these examples, Alisher Navoi states that there are four independent phonemes in the old Uzbek language that differ from each other in terms of length and length. The first of them is "o" (dom) of normal length, the second is the wood on which the bird sits, because it is shorter than the first, it is the first level short o', the third is the front of the house, and because it is shorter than the second, it is the second short o' of the degree, the fourth one is a short o' of the third degree, since the lattice (door net) is shorter than the third.

The number of labial vowels in the language of Abulghazi Bahadirkhann's works is four, and they are as follows:

1. u - tongue back, upper narrow, labial vowel.
2. y - front of the tongue, upper narrow, labial vowel.
3. o - tongue back, middle wide, labial vowel.
4. ö - front of the tongue, middle wide, labial vowel.

In order to come to a certain conclusion about the labial vowels used in Abulghazi's works, it is appropriate to analyze the following excerpts from his works: Esli had a son named Shaban, and they made him Khan. He followed the path of his fathers, became good to goods and bad to bads, killed his father on the throne for twenty years, and moved to the land of his great-grandfathers. (Sh.Tar. p. 35) or ... After destroying Nishapur, Tolikhan marched on Herat. When you got close to Herat, he sent Zanbur, a cavalry servant, as an ambassador and told the nobles and nobles of Herat that you should not die and your sons and daughters become prisoners (Sh.T., p. 77.).

Analyzing the microtext, we see that there are labial vowels in the following places: o'g'li, ul, yurgan, yo'ldin, yurub, bo'lub, o'lturub, ulug', ko'ch, tushub, ko'chib, To'lixon, Nishapur, so'ng, yurudi, Zanbur, yubordi, o'zingiz, o'lub, o'g'lon-ushoq, bo'lmag'ay (son, he, walked, on the road, walked, became, killed, great, moved, descended, moved, Tolikhan, Nishapur, then, walked, Zanbur, sent, yourself, die, boy-child, do not be).

Although it is said that there are theoretically 6 vowels in the modern Uzbek literary language, even today there is a feature of distinguishing the meaning of labial vowels. If we pay attention to the passage above, we can see that the labial vowels in words like olmaq (form of the verb to be) - olmaq (to die), bolmaq (the verb to be also acts as a conjunction) – bolmaq (to divide, to separate), tush (a dream in sleep) – tüş (stem of the verb to fall) can have different meanings. The opinions of academicians Ganijon Abdurahmanov and Alibek Rustamov are very important regarding the number and quality of labial vowels. According to these two scientists, the phonemes o and ö have converged and become one phoneme as a result of shifting to o in the modern Uzbek literary language and Uzbek dialects and dialects without synharmonism. But in other Turkic languages, as well as in Uzbek dialects and dialects without synharmonism, o and ö are independent phonemes. The position of u and y in ancient Turkic is the same as u and y in modern Uzbek. Even in Old Turkic, u and y are independent phonemes. For example, uch (the ending) □ ych (the number 3).⁶

We can learn from Alisher Navoi's valuable information about the fact that the labial vowels in the old Uzbek language are distinguished by their quality, that is, their length and length. Alisher Navoi states that the word vovli erur with simple long vowel can be rhymed with the short u, i.e. the extended zammali hur ح (hooray) va dur د (pearl) words with simple long u g'urur

⁵ Алишер Навоий. Асарлар .14-том.Т.: 1966. 114-бет.

⁶ Абдурахмонов Ф., Рустамов А. Қадимги туркий тил. – Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1982, 8-бет.

غرور (pride) va zarur ضرور (need). This example tells us about two sounds: one is regular u and the other is short u.

In the works of Abulghazi, we see that there are vowels i and q that differ from each other according to the correct direction of the tongue (horizontally). In the history of the Uzbek language, it is known that these vowels have three different aspects. In particular, Alisher Navoi also left valuable information about the vowels i in the 15th century and writes about it: "...and an example of a bow cannot be found more than three movements".⁷ This shows that in the Uzbek language of the 15th century, there were three vowels i, which differed from each other in long and short, and had the feature of separating meaning.

Alisher Navoi distinguishes both of these vowels by the quality of long and short. In particular, our great poet writes that it is possible to rhyme a word with a bow meaning a simple i with a word kasrali with a short i: "...va yo bila kasra orasidag'i bu nav□dur, andoqki, اغبر ag'qr va باغبر bag'qr alfozin sadir صادرva qadir قادر alfozi bila qofiya qilsa bo'lur, ta'xir va tag'yir alfozi bila ham bo'lur (...and this is a type between bila and kasra, but it can be rhymed with aghbr aghqr wabaghir baghqr alfozin sadir şadrwa qadir qadr alfozi, and with tahir and taghyr alfozi)".⁸

If we observe the vowel system in the historical works of Abulghazi Bahadir Khan, we see that 10 independent phonemes are preserved in them. If we compare them with the language of the written monuments of the 16th century, according to the summary of the information about vowels in "Muhokamatul-lughatayn", we see that the Uzbek language of the 15th century had the following vowel sounds:

1. Substantial alphabet - long a.
2. Has normal elongation a.
3. Short a, which is represented by hoyi havvaz.
4. Simple u expressed by Vov.
5. Short u expressed by zamma.
6. U of normal length.
7. First degree short u.
8. Short o' of the second degree.
9. Short o' of the third degree.
10. Has normal length i represented by an arc.
11. Short i expressed by kasra.
12. Long i.
13. The vowel i.

Based on this, according to Professor Ergash Umarov, there were 13 vowel sounds in the old Uzbek language. 9 of the vowels are phonemes. Alisher Navoi showed the difference between vowels only by long-shortness and narrow-width. A similar classification can be seen in the dictionaries of the poet's works. This shows that for the old Uzbek language, not hardness or softness, but length-shortness and narrow-width were the main features. If we take into account the phoneme variants, the number of vowels in Abulghazi Khan's works can be shown in this way.

⁷ Алишер Навоий. Асарлар. 14- том. - Т.: 1967 .115-6.

⁸ Алишер Навоий. Асарлар. 14- том. - Т.: 1967 .115-6.